

Pedagogical Skills in The Use of National Heritage Values in The Process of Development of Innovative Education in Higher Education

**Author(s), ALIJONOVA M. R, MAMATOV. R. R, QAMBAROV A.M,
AND
OTABOYEVA Z.G**

1

**International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science
(IJARBAS.COM)**

Email: editor@jarbas.com editor.ijarbas@gmail.com Website: ijarbas.com

Published By

Abstract:

The article reveals the features of the interaction of the individual with the social environment, pedagogical ways are being put forward to strengthen the purposeful influence of social factors on the education of students, the formation of their moral values.

IJARBAS

Accepted 1 March 2020
Published 10 March 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3707015

Keywords: social environment, spontaneous and purposeful factors of socialization, personality, students, social and developing situation,

About Author

Author(s), Teacher of department,
Tashkent State Agricultural University Andijan
Branch, Uzbekistan "Pedagogy, Psychology and Physical Education"

In Uzbekistan, a great deal of work has been done on the years of independence, preserving cultural values and national traditions. It is noteworthy that in Uzbekistan, the national culture of the Uzbek people is deeply rooted in psychological and ethnical characteristics, despite centuries of rich educational experience.

With the development of the world community, there is also the development and transformation of the system of values, with the technical and technological progress, the increasing importance of material and legal values, and the tendency of cultural and civilization values to rise. One of the most important tasks set by the state today is the development of the spiritual values and the deportation of the generation. This task is one of the most important social institutions and is part of the educational system. This time, a comprehensive set of strategies and measures for up-to-date instruction and assessment of modernization will come to fruition. Nowadays one of the prerequisites for effective training of higher education is to provide students with the opportunity to build their own interests and needs, and to provide high quality educational institutions for the development of spiritual, moral, human and professional education.

The institution of higher education should not only be the center of specialists' training, but also the cultural, educational and cultural-moral space of the kangaroo, which must always be based on human and moral values.

In the scientific and educational system of higher education institutions the task of shaping the national mentality of students is of particular importance. In the process

of making this nation's historical and cultural feelings and values, the English language is formed, and the person becomes the carrier and successor of the culture.

Using the pedagogical system of formation of national values in students, we take into account the current socio-cultural situation and the impact on education and the formation of identity. Specifically, we are based on the 21st Century Teaching List, which is a cultured, cynical human worldview that shapes the most important principle of humanism and global humanity, as well as one of the most important humanities. So, we have decided to take into account higher education and internal factors of educational process.

The main factors that contribute to the development of national English, national and cultural worldviews are the mysteries of values and the dominant ideology of life, both small and medium, and the culture of socialization.

It should be emphasized separately that the formation of national values in the periods of development has not been given much attention to the internal factors influencing the design and psychosocial characteristics of the students, which in turn influences the results of educational activities.

Internal factors can be the impact of each individual's personal experience, commitment to dignity, customization and socialization in the ever-expanding multicultural environment. [2]. Internal and external factors make the relationship between students' commitment, and their commitment to the people and the world, mentality, vision, and rules visible. Inside and out, the new Englishman's help comes from the concept of "I", which will bring national identity to the UK.

The educational process in the CTS is a learning process and student-led meeting, thanks to the support of the most important forms of training and organization of activities, training and training of the subject-matter, and the high level of respect. The practicality and effectiveness of the educational process in CTMs is directly dependent on the existing conditions.

Every student should be the carrier of the cognitive and socio-psychoanalysis, which is the basis for the training of personnel. Higher education has a strong influence on the psychological convenience, the teaching and learning activities of the student-led human relations, the training of students and their ability to satisfy the humanistic environment.

An important goal in the development and training of the quality of educational activity was to establish an educational and organizational activity of the general public in institutions of higher education.

It is linked with the development of universal education, multidisciplinary and multifaceted, as well as broadening the areas of social partnership for the purpose of achieving the desired result. The development of the unified activity is reflected in the development. Only such cooperation enables effective interaction between the national culture and the vernacular of the vernal equinox.

Scientists who are interested in the basics of educational conception are able to create the basis for the educational, scientific, and communicative approach to the creation of all the components (purpose, subject, activity, meeting, relationship,

material base) of the discipline. The characteristics of the inner world are the most abundant in the world. [2].

If we have the experience we have learned, it is important to provide and maintain the functions that the training system provides:

1) The *development of personalization* of students will be aimed at supporting and stimulating the most needed changes, providing students with the highest legal education and the establishment of a comprehensive training system;

2) the *integration of the primary, the first, and the most conspicuous educational implications*;

3) the *linking of pedagogical educational processes* that influence the formation of *personal, academic, pedagogical and pedagogical staff*;

4) *environment tally oriented*, that is, the educational purpose of the pedagogical orphanage, the use of intrinsic, educational, and transport (natural, social and architectural) environments;

5) *Activity-Dependentation of national values*, as well as providing students with a variety of activities;

6) *social protection of students and teachers, neutralization* of negative influence of the external environment on the processes of education and personality formation:

7) *consisting of frequent workloads*, teacher training, and training sessions to minimize the negative impact on the student's formation;

8) In the *event that the* student's life style, student interests and abilities are not involved in the development and development of the family and community, education will be able to achieve the necessary conditions.

Pedagogical inventory of national values is an important prerequisite for successful development of psychological mechanisms in the process of development.

During the pedagogical meeting, students gain 3 levels of critical recognition of national culture: analytical (appreciation, understanding and personal giving), evaluator (personal appreciation, self-importance and self-esteem). customization, "build for the sake of the Ash"

People have learned from the psychological mechanisms of traditional knowledge and motives - motives - feelings and attitudes - skills and habits - the movement of lines and the nose of loose ends.

References

- Maslow, A. Motivation and Love / A. Maslow. 3d e., P. c English -Spb : Peter, 2008. - 352 pp.
- Vygotsky L.S. Educational Psychology. M.: AST, Astral, Hrithanel, 2008. - 671 c.

Cite this article:

Author(s), ALIJONOVA M. R, MAMATOV. R. R, QAMBAROV A.M, AND OTABOYEVA Z.G (2020). **Title:** “Pedagogical Skills in The Use of National Heritage Values in The Process of Development of Innovative Education in Higher Education”. **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 23-31. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3707015 , Issue: 3, Vol.: 2, Article: 2, Month: March, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

PAGE: 9

1

International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science (IJARBAS.COM)

Email: editor@jarbas.com editor.ijarbas@gmail.com Website: jarbas.com

Published By

